

INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR PLACE IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING AT AN EARLY STAGE

Urinboyeva G.D¹, Urinboyeva Guluzro Dushayevna²

Lecturer of the department of English Phonetics, faculty of Foreign Languages, Andijan State University Andijan, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6604223>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th May 2022

Accepted: 14th May 2022

Online: 31th May 2022

KEY WORDS

Pedagogical environment, communication, development of personality, effectiveness of modern methods, interactive teaching, communication, process of teaching, interactive methods.

ABSTRACT

The stage of development of state society is characterized by profound socio-economic transformations, when a person is required not only knowledge and skills, but also developed personal qualities that would allow him to actively participate in creative activities. In this regard, education faces new challenges: the school should focus on creating optimal conditions for the development of each child, focus not on learning, but on the formation of students' ability to independently comprehend the environment.

According to research, the optimal for the development of personality is a dialogic pedagogical environment in which the individual is recognized as valuable, free and respected. The learning process in the context of dialogue is an active interaction and communication of its participants, ie interaction, which is carried out using appropriate methods. The problem of interactive use in the educational process was the focus of such researchers as O. Yelnikova, G. Kobernik, O. Kobernik, O. Komar, T. Pobirchenko, O. Pometun, etc., who justify the use of interactive to enhance the effectiveness of the learning process .

The purpose of the article is to determine, theoretically substantiate and experimentally test the didactic principles of using interactive methods in the process

of teaching students. According to the goal, the following tasks were formulated:

1. Analyze the state of problem development in pedagogical theory and practice; to determine the degree, structure and features of the use of interactive teaching methods at an early stage, to classify them.
2. To substantiate the age characteristics of learners at an early age as a prerequisite for the introduction of interactive methods in the learning process.
3. To develop, scientifically substantiate and experimentally test the model of realization of didactic bases of application of interactive methods in the process of language education of learners. The scientific novelty of the study is that for the first time:

- identified ways to use interactive methods in the process of language education of students;
- developed and scientifically substantiated a model for the implementation of interactive methods in the process of language education of students, which revealed the main components: the goals of the learning process; principles; interactive teaching methods; educational activities in class; improved communicative competence.

Further development was given to:

- classification of interactive methods according to the criteria of the number of participants, the nature of tasks, methodological purpose, and stage of the lesson, which allowed to increase the effectiveness of the formation of communicative competence in students;
- theoretical provisions on the essence of the concepts of “interactive method”, “interaction”, features of the structure of the interactive method, and the learning process using interactive methods.

The key to the effectiveness of pedagogical activities of teachers is the knowledge of the age characteristics of students. According to psychologists, the leading activity at this stage is training, which in turn contributes to the formation of age-related activities, reflection, and internal action plans. The development of all mental processes is marked by the growth of their arbitrariness, controllability, and awareness. In the works of famous scientists, there is convincing evidence that a child learns a foreign language easier than an adult. The advantage of younger students is the potential for great opportunities for long-term memory.

The growing intellectual potential of second-graders creates a good basis for the

perception and assimilation of socio-cultural information, which should be saturated with the content of foreign language learning if the latter is really aimed at students' mastery of intercultural foreign language communication.

Primary school children like a foreign language. They want to get acquainted with the life of the country whose language they are studying, its people, and its spiritual values related to the world of the child. First of all, the factor of the novelty of the subject and socio-cultural information embedded in it works. Research studies show that the saturation of the subject content of a foreign language lesson with socio-cultural information stimulates cognitive-communicative motivation for learning, thereby activating the mental abilities of students. Activation of thinking enhances the work of attention and memory. Modeling life situations of communication with native speakers (foreign peers, their parents, teachers, representatives of the domestic sphere, etc.) has significant potential to ensure adequate assimilation of socio-cultural information, especially etiquette; for children to compare their interests, views, preferences with the same personal manifestations of foreign peers in standard simulated situations; to create a social situation of child development, which in real life arises in the process of its communication with adults and interaction with peers. This is how the child is brought up, developed, and changed and his self-esteem becomes more reasonable, reflective, and differentiated, so the child begins to become more aware of his interests, motives, etc. [3]

It is important to use different activities in the learning process that will ensure the

joint work of the left and right hemispheres of the brain. Thus, if you combine the process of learning a foreign language with the feelings, experiences, emotions, lives of students, and their interests, it will ensure the organic unity of intellectual and emotional components for the holistic development of personality. Assigning a foreign language is a way to enrich yourself through established communication skills or levels of communicative competence.

How to organize the learning process so that students can easily use a foreign language for communication in real-life situations and for acquiring knowledge; to navigate the socio-cultural aspects of the country whose language is being studied? Practice shows that this is largely facilitated by the atmosphere of collective communication, organized on the basis of communicative situations. Communication in such situations creates a strong and constant interest in learning English and gives students the opportunity to consciously learn foreign language material. Such communication is emotionally colored, imbued with individual experiences, it brings joy, and interest in joint activities creates important prerequisites for success, which can not but be of interest to both students and teachers.

Interactive technologies effectively contribute to the formation of skills and abilities, the development of values, creating an atmosphere of cooperation, interaction and enable the teacher to become a true leader of the student body. For me personally, it is a desire to find a reasonable balance between academic and pragmatic knowledge, skills and abilities. Thanks to such modern technologies, students learn to be democratic, think critically, make informed decisions, and

therefore, there is constant cooperation between students during the lesson, the student and teacher are equal, that is, they know how to do and understand what they do and why.

Using interactive technologies in English lessons is very relevant today because it caught my attention. The modern teacher must use such technologies in his practice to make it interesting for students to learn English. And most importantly - to be effective learning. While preparing English lessons, I carefully consider each stage of the lesson, select the appropriate clarity for the topic, interesting forms of work.

A lesson cannot exist without modern innovative technologies. Based on the above, I propose to consider the question, what is interactive learning?

Interactive learning is a special form of organization of cognitive activity, which has a specific, predictable goal - to create comfortable learning conditions in which each student feels his success, intellectual ability to eliminate the dominance of one thought over another. During interactive learning, students learn to be democratic, communicate with other people, think constructively, make informed decisions. [8]

A feature of interactive learning is the preparation of children for life, social activity in society and a democratic state governed by the rule of law. Lessons give students basic cognitive skills of retelling abstract, ready-made information detached from children's lives and experiences. Lessons captivate pupils, arouse their interest and motivation, teach them to think and act independently.

The use of interactive technologies in English lessons suggests that they are a means of creating an atmosphere of

friendliness and understanding, fear disappears, activity increases, self-confidence arises, there is a desire to succeed, creativity develops. It is in such an atmosphere that one can expect productive assimilation of educational material and the formation and development of skills for its practical use, enrichment of social and communicative experience of students, increase cognitive activity and motivation of students. Our own experience proves that the use of interactive technologies allows:

- make learning interesting;
- learn to formulate their own opinion;
- to model various social situations;
- build relationships in the group;
- teach to respect alternative opinion;
- enrich the social experience of students;
- develop skills of independent creative work;
- be able to find compromises.

Numerous methods of interactive learning provide a choice for teachers: "Brainstorming", "Author's chair", "Circle of ideas", "Learning to learn", pair and group work, the method of associations, role-playing games. However, it is important to emphasize the need for careful preparation for each lesson, which uses interactive types of work. After all, it is necessary, firstly, to alternate them with traditional tasks and, thus, to anticipate and avoid student fatigue, and, secondly, it is necessary that innovative tasks help to create situations of success for each student.

It should be noted that a component of the content of socio-cultural competence, which means a system of ideas about the main national traditions, customs and the country whose language is studied, as well as a system of skills and abilities to behave based on this knowledge, are also elements

of pupils' English folklore. small forms (rhymes, counters, poems, songs).

Using poetry and rhyming in English lessons at school, pupils' pronunciation improves and becomes clear, emotional and expressive.

Group forms of work can be used to consolidate or activate lexical material. The activity to activate vocabulary is "Brainstorming". Before vocabulary dictation or independent work, you can give pupils the task to remember as many words on the topic and make a list of words; first in pairs and then in fours. After completing the exercise, make a general list of words on the board.

Group forms of work are widely used to create monologues. For example, when studying the topic "Friends", students make a portrait of an ideal friend, fixing pictures with schematic representations of different character traits on the red (positive) or black (negative) half of the heart on the board. For example, My ideal friend is kind. My ideal friend is not lazy.

A similar task can be performed while studying other topics. Students can work as designers by posting pictures of furniture on a poster room ("My flat" theme, or there) / or by posting their wishes on a Christmas tree ("Holidays" theme).

Another exercise for creating collective monologues is the "accordion". Each student writes one sentence on the topic and folds the sheet so that the next student does not see the previous statement. After everyone has written a sentence, one of the students reads the message.

The study of foreign languages today is carried out in a broad socio-cultural context, has a clear cultural direction. In modern practice of teaching foreign languages in Ukrainian schools, the project method is

widely used, which provides reliance on the creativity of students, encouraging them to research.

Project work - a type of work, the purpose of which is to prepare the final product in English - album, presentation of information. Project work is ideal for multi-level groups, as each task can be completed by students with different levels of training. In the process of project activities, students actually communicate with each other and with the world around them in English. Samples of tasks for project work that have recently been most remembered by students: "My family, my friends", "Student and his environment", "Appearance": a story about yourself with support (for primary school students), where the support is made in the form of hexagons folded into a kind of "flower", where on each "petal" the student must reveal a question (his name, age, place of residence, school, school friends, pets, preferences, etc.); "Family trees", "Food and products".

Of course, in real practice you often have to deal with mixed types of projects. As an example of creative projects offered in the first year of study, I would like to cite the following: the creation of drawings depicting monsters, which can be used to study the topic of "Body". When defending projects, children describe their drawings using learned lexical items.

Every year the issue of ensuring the proper level of information services of the educational process becomes more relevant. There is a steady trend towards expanding the impact of information and communication technologies (ICT) on the education system.

Information and communication technologies: is a set of methods, tools and techniques used to select, process, store,

present, transmit a variety of data and materials needed to improve the efficiency of various activities. The introduction of ICT in the educational process stimulates interest in educational activities, promotes the formation of logical and creative thinking, promotes the development of students' abilities and the formation of information culture.

In English lessons I use ICT to find and get more information; expanding and deepening knowledge using the Internet, more fully meet the personality-oriented needs of students; formation and consolidation of skills, techniques, methods, skills of their application. Younger students enjoy watching cartoons in English.

The level of development and features of the psyche affect the pace of student work in class. And if you take into account the state of health and even today's mood, the difference in speed and quality of student work is significant. Lessons should captivate children, actualize their motivational processes, teach independence in thinking and acting. "A feature of interactive learning is to prepare students for life and civic activity in civil society and democratic rule of law in classes in any subject of the school curriculum." [6, p.82] The use of interactive technologies makes certain demands on the structure of lessons.

The purpose of the motivation phase is to draw students' attention to the problem and arouse interest in it. Motivation allows children to realize that they will now begin to study another subject, that they are faced with other tasks. Here are used techniques that create problematic situations, surprise children, interest in the content and process, phenomena and events, formulating problematic issues.

Directly, the organization of interactive learning involves the simulation of various life situations, joint problem solving based on the analysis of circumstances and the situation, the use of role-playing games. Among the interactive technologies are widely used such as: brainstorming, microphone, circle of ideas, work in small groups, position loans, press method, aquarium, travel, role-playing games and others.

All of the above does not mean that only interactive learning should be implemented. All levels of knowledge and all kinds of methods and technologies are important for the student's educational activity. O. Pometun in his work [6] presents a table showing the strengths and weaknesses of passive, active and interactive learning. Undoubtedly, in today's world a successful person can be one who can think, understand the essence of things, comprehend ideas and concepts, and already on this basis be able to search for the necessary information, interpret it and apply it in specific conditions. This is what interactive technologies contribute to. In order to overcome the difficulties in the use of interactive technologies, the following should be taken into account:

- Interaction takes a lot of time to prepare. It is necessary to begin with the gradual application of individual elements. It is better to prepare several interactive classes well than to spend hastily prepared "games".
- You can conduct an organizational lesson with students and create rules for classroom work. In the beginning, you should use simple technologies - work in pairs, small groups, brainstorming and more.

- Interactive learning is not an end in itself, but a tool that enables the implementation of personality-oriented learning.

- If the use of an interactive model does not work, you should review the strategy used and use it carefully.

- For the effective application of interactive learning, in particular, in order to cover all the necessary material and study it in detail, the teacher must carefully plan their work to: give students tasks for preliminary training; select for the lesson such interactive exercises that would give students the key to mastering the topic; during the most interactive exercises to give students enough time to think about the task to exclude the mechanics of execution; one or two interactive exercises can be used in one lesson, instead of their kaleidoscope; in-depth discussion based on the results of the interactive exercise is very important; to conduct quick surveys, independent homework on a variety of materials on topics that were not related to interactive tasks.

To effectively monitor the learning process using an interactive learning model, the teacher must first study and think through the basic and additional material (texts, sample documents, examples, situations, tasks for groups, etc.); carefully plan and develop classes; motivate students to study by selecting the most interesting cases, provide a variety of methods to attract students' attention, set them up for work, maintain the discipline necessary for normal work.

After a few carefully prepared lessons, the teacher will be able to feel how the attitude of students towards him has changed, as well as the atmosphere in the classroom - and this will be an additional incentive to work with interactive technologies.

It should be noted that interactive learning technologies include a clearly planned, expected learning outcome, some interactive methods and techniques that stimulate the learning process and mental and educational conditions and procedures by which to achieve the intended results

Thanks to these technologies, I was able not only to increase the motivation of students to learn the language, but also to improve the atmosphere in the classroom, to increase the knowledge of my students in all types of speech activities. At each lesson they expect something interesting, unusual. The pupils enthusiastically began to prepare for lessons and work actively.

Therefore, interactive technologies help me as a teacher not only to develop students' speech skills, but also to form their intellectual and speech abilities.

Much attention is paid to the development of a culture of communication, enriching students' understanding of the country whose language is being studied, deepening their linguistic knowledge. Active activities

are carried out aimed at fostering a positive attitude of students to a foreign language, culture and life. The concept of the role of language as an element of people's culture and the need to use it as an important means of intercultural communication is formed. language English phonetics interactive Skillful use of interactive techniques in learning contributes to the formation of critical thinking skills and cognitive interests of students. Pupils begin to feel confident, free to express their thoughts and calmly accept comments, consider themselves active participants in the learning process.

Thus, interactive methods contribute to the efficiency and quality of the learning process. In interactive lessons, students have the opportunity to:

- expand their cognitive capabilities;
- interact with the teacher as an equal participant in the situation;
- work in a team;
- express your own opinion;
- create "success situations".

References:

1. English language and literature at school. - 2008. -№24. p.5-7.
2. English language and literature at school. - 2009. -№26. p.17-19.
3. Zakharchenko A.O. Features of the organization of English language teaching at an early stage // English language in primary school. - 2008. -№1
4. Karpyuk O.D. Textbook "English2" - K.: "Textbook" 2012.
5. Karpyuk O.D. Textbook "English3" - K.: "Textbook" 2013.
6. Karpyuk O.D. Textbook "English3" - K.: "Textbook" 2015.
7. Panchenko A., Pementun O. Interactive learning technologies: Theory, experience: Method. Manual./ K.: APN – 136p.
8. Pometun O. Modern lesson. Interactive learning technologies / O. Pometun, L. Pirozhenko / K.: "Publishing House ASK", 2003.-192p.
9. Phil N.Yu. Didactic mosaic: Kharkiv.: Morning. - 2003. - p.226-270.